

Conference Abstract

Conservation of the weather loach (*Misgurnus fossilis*) in near-natural habitat pools

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Abstract

The weather loach (*Misgurnus fossilis*) is highly specialized in its habitat choice and adaptation to standing or slow flowing water bodies with soft sediment and macrophytes, sometimes bearing low oxygen levels, but tends to be a weak interspecific competitor. The widespread loss of those special habitats, ongoing climate change and arriving Neozooans are main factors that drive the dramatic decline of *M. fossilis* populations. The arrival of Asian weather loaches *Misgurnus bipartitus* and *M. anguillicaudatus* and moreover *Percottus glenii* to habitats within Europe as a direct competitor for the same food and habitat sources, tremendously increases the pressure on the last populations. Furthermore, hybridization between *Misgurnus* species is possible and may result in production of viable offspring. Not only the populations and their habitats themselves are at risk, also the genetic integrity and the whole genetic variability of this species is facing the threat of being obliterated. *M. fossilis* from different populations are used to maintain reproductive stocks for an ex-situ program to conserve *M. fossilis* in Austria. There are two main ways to keep weather loaches in different setups for controlled reproduction and long-term husbandry. One is to keep them in larger fish ponds and on the other hand to keep them in aquaria. Each strategy has its benefits and downsides. The larger outdoor version in fish ponds suits the natural habitat use of *M. fossilis* and reduces density problems like disease spread, follows a natural rhythm and requires lower maintenance efforts. Nevertheless, it comes with some downsides. In order to keep several populations in parallel, normally large sized ponds are used, which may not be available for small scale conservation projects. The lack of control and the broad range of

habitat factors (different primary- and secondary production, uncontrolled predation and competitors, water chemistry and other abiotic factors...) is challenging. Husbandry in aquariums is easier to control but has some severe downsides like the high costs for larger aquariums, the technical infrastructure and their permanent costs and need for maintenance, as well as energy costs and low secondary production, as well as density problems and fast disease spread, especially in connected systems. We came up with an alternative solution, to combine the two systems. We installed four large, round semi natural habitat pools, with about 15m³ (400cm x 120cm, round shaped) of water volume each, and several movable planters to provide adequate habitat conditions (Suppl. material 1). The substrate consists of a 5-10cm thick layer of leaf litter and several oak branches. Each habitat pool was seeded with daphnia, isopods and other invertebrates to start a natural food chain. These setups show high zooplankton production, guarantee easy access to the fish, widely controllable conditions, and low maintenance requirements. The semi natural conditions in those habitat pools benefit an overall good health status, growth and body condition of the brood stock for the upcoming reproductive seasons.

Presenting author

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Conservation of the weather loach (*Misgurnus fossilis*) in near-natural habitat pools [doi](#)

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